

Complexation Reactions of Dialkyltin Dichloride with Chromotropic Acid

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Potentiometric titrations of dialkyltin dichloride with chromotropic acid (sodium salt) in varying molar ratios have been carried out. The formation of only dialkyltin monochloromtropate chelates have been indicated in the lower pH range.

THE first study of the metal chelate formation by the disodium salt of chromotropic acid appears to have been made with iron ions by Heller and Schwarzenbach¹. These workers determined the first ($Ka_1 = 4.365 \times 10^{-6}$) and second ($Ka_2 = 2.512 \times 10^{-16}$) ionisation constants of the acid itself. It has been reported that the acid forms chelates with a number of metal ions²⁻¹⁸. During present investigations, a study of complexation reactions of dialkyltin dichloride with disodium salt of chromotropic acid has been carried out by potentiometric technique.

Experimental

Dialkyltin dichlorides, R_2SnCl_2 ($R = CH_3, C_2H_5$ and C_4H_9) were purified by sublimation or distillation. Disodium salt of chromotropic acid was E. Merck product and was purified by recrystallisation from aqueous alcohol.

All solutions were made up with conductivity water whereas 70% dioxane was used for the study of dibutyltin systems because of insolubility of dibutyltin dichloride in water. Constant ionic strength was maintained by using 0.1M potassium nitrate.

pH measurements were carried out at the room temperature with a Cambridge Bench type pH meter, standardised against 0.05M solution of potassium hydrogen phthalate ($pH = 4.00$) using saturated calomel electrode and high range (pH 1-13) glass electrode.

Results and Discussion

Potentiometric titration of dimethyltin dichloride in the presence of equimolar concentration of disodium salt of chromotropic acid (Fig. 1) with caustic soda shows a lowering in the pH which indicates the formation of chelated complex species in which the hydroxyl protons become less firmly held due to coordinate bond formation. However, there is only a very weak inflexion at two moles of alkali ($m = 2$, $m =$ moles of alkali added per mole metal ion). A sharp inflexion has been observed at three moles of alkali; the nature of the inflexion is similar to that with the ligand itself. This inflexion at three moles may be due to either of the two possibilities: (i) the formation of a hydroxoanion derivative (B)

Fig. 1. Potentiometric titrations of dimethyltin dichloride with sodium hydroxide (N/10) in the presence of 1, 2 and 3 moles of chromotropic acid in the nitrogen atmosphere.

- I. Δ , 5 ml M/40 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
- II. \bullet , 5 ml M/40 metal + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
- III. \circ , 5 ml M/40 metal + 5 ml M/40 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
- IV. \times , 5 ml M/40 metal + 10 ml M/40 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
- V. \times , 5 ml M/40 metal + 15 ml M/40 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
(Made upto volume 50 ml in each case).

or (ii) hydrolysis of the complex at higher pH into the hydroxide and free ligand which may interact with the third mole of alkali as indicated below:

Out of the above, the former course appears to be much more probable due to the observation of the formation of similar mono-hydroxo derivatives with a number of other ligands (like catechol and tiron). The ill-defined inflexion at two moles ($m = 2$) appears

to be due to weaker chelation involving a six membered ring. This would mean that the inflexion at two moles of alkali could be expected only at a higher pH value and in view of the narrower gap between the two points of inflexions, the first one could be much less marked.

In the titration of equimolar concentration of diethyltin dichloride and the ligand lowering in pH begins from 0.6 moles, whereas with dimethyl analogue, lowering starts immediately after the addition of the base. Unlike dimethyltin dichloride, even a very weak inflexion has not been observed in this case at two moles ($m = 2$) but a sharp inflexion at three moles ($m = 3$) appears as in the case of dimethyltin dichloride.

Fig. 2. Potentiometric titrations of diethyltin dichloride with sodium hydroxide (N/10) in presence of 1, 2 and 3 moles of chromotropic acid in the nitrogen atmosphere.

- I, Δ , 5 ml M/10 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
- II, \bullet , 5 ml M/10 metal + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
- III, \circ , 5 ml M/10 metal + 5 ml M/40 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
- IV, \times , 5 ml M/10 metal + 10 ml M/40 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
- V, Δ , 5 ml M/10 metal + 15 ml M/40 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
(Made upto volume 50 ml in each case).

The titration of dibutyltin dichloride (carried out in 70% dioxane) in the presence of chromotropic acid in molar ratio 1 : 1 shows only slight lowering in pH in acidic medium and a sharp inflexion at three moles ($m=3$) as observed in the earlier cases also (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. Potentiometric titrations of dibutyltin dichloride with sodium hydroxide in the presence of 1 mole of chromotropic acid in the nitrogen atmosphere.

- I, Δ , 5 ml M/40 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
- II, \bullet , 5 ml M/40 metal + 5 ml M/40 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3
- III, \circ , 5 ml M/10 metal + 10 ml M/40 ligand + 5 ml (M) KNO_3 (made up to volume 50 ml in each case)

Similar titrations of dialkyltin dichlorides, R_2SnCl_2 , ($\text{R} = \text{CH}_3$ and C_2H_5), have been carried out with alkali in the presence of two and three moles of chromotropic acid (Figs. 1 and 2).

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